

Exploring Mention Motivation of Algorithm Entities in Full-text of Academic Papers

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Introduction

As an important component of the AI era, algorithms have been proposed, improved, and used in academic papers, providing scholars with important research objects and rich research tools. To understand the development of algorithms, scholars have analyzed the diffusion and academic influence of algorithms in academic papers (Wang & Zhang, 2020; Zha et al., 2019). However, existing works ignored that authors mention algorithms with different motivations (we call mention motivation), which reflects the various importance of algorithms. Suppose the mention motivation of the algorithm can be identified, we can get deeper insights into the algorithm’s role, contribution, and influence in a specific paper or domain, thereby conducting fine-grained algorithm evaluation, recommendation and other work (Tuarob et al., 2019).

Taking the Natural Language Processing (NLP) field as an example, we extracted algorithms from the full text of papers and then automatically classified mention motivations to study the features of algorithms shown in motivations. Specifically, we aim to answer two research questions:

RQ1: What is the distribution of mention motivation for algorithms in the NLP domain?

RQ2: How do the proportions of different mention motivations for algorithms with high mention frequency differ?

In this article, we define the “algorithm” as nouns or noun phrases that refer to algorithms in academic papers, namely, the algorithm entity.

Methodology

The proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (*ACL*) conference were used to identify algorithm entities and their mention motivation. We downloaded the full-text papers published from 1979 to 2020 in XML format from the *ACL reference corpus* (<https://acl-arc.comp.nus.edu.sg/>) and *ACL anthology repository* (<https://github.com/acl-org/acl-anthology/tree/master/data/xml>).

Algorithm entity extraction

Wang & Zhang (2020) annotated the algorithm entities (entities A) sentences in the full text of *ACL* conference papers published from 1979 to 2015. We preprocessed the entities and sentences to train three commonly used entity recognition models. Table 1

shows the BERT+BiLSTM+CRF got the highest F₁ value; therefore, we chose it to predict candidate algorithm entities in the remaining papers published from 2016 to 2020. A total of 1,988 independent algorithm entities (entities B) were recognized from candidate algorithm entities by manual annotation and expert review. Combining entities B with entities A, we obtained 3,033 entities which can be standardized as 1,651 algorithms (since one algorithm has multiple names). Using the same method as Wang & Zhang (2020), we compiled an algorithm dictionary and used the dictionary-matching to identify 107,554 sentences mentioning the 3,033 algorithm entities in all *ACL* papers.

Table 1. Performance of the extraction models

Model	Precision	Recall	F ₁
Bi-lstm+CRF	0.872	0.901	0.886
Bert+CRF	0.953	0.962	0.957
Bert+Bi-lstm+CRF	0.970	0.959	0.964

Identifying the mention motivation of algorithms

(1) Annotating training dataset. We designed a four-category framework to classify motivations, including *Mention* (only introducing or mentioning the algorithm), *Use* (using the algorithm directly), *Compare* (using the algorithm and comparing it with others), and *Improve* (modifying the algorithm and then using the modified version). A total of 6,400 algorithm sentences were randomly selected from 353 papers, and two annotators were invited to assign one motivation for each sentence. The interrater reliability between the annotators was 0.76 (*Cohen’s Kappa*), and any inconsistent results were re-annotated after discussion by annotators. We obtained a final training dataset of 6,261 sentences.

(2) Training classification models and predicting mention motivations. We used two corpora to train four pre-trained models: the original training corpus, and the training corpus that was augmented through synonym replacement and word insertion. The performance of the four models, including Bert, SciBert, XLNet and T5, is shown in Table 2. The SciBert model trained with the augmented corpus performed the best, with a macro-F₁ of 74.3%. Using this model, we determined the motivation of 107,554 sentences mentioning algorithm entities.

Table 2. The performance of different models in motivation classification

Data	Model	macro-P	macro-R	macro-F ₁
Original corpus	Bert	0.699	0.729	0.713
	SciBert	0.721	0.745	0.730
	XLNet	0.704	0.730	0.714
	T5	0.686	0.675	0.678
Augmented corpus	BERT	0.708	0.759	0.730
	SciBert	0.743	0.757	0.743
	XLNet	0.712	0.730	0.710
	T5	0.741	0.741	0.740

Results

The distribution and evolution of motivation

Out of the 107,554 algorithm sentences in ACL papers, the distribution of four motivations is as follows: Use (10,058), Mention (25,850), Compare (10,058), Improve (1,397). Approximately 70% of sentences express the direct use of an algorithm. Figure 1 shows the evolution of the proportion of motivations, with “use” consistently being the highest and “improve” being the lowest. In papers published from 1979 to 1985, there was no one “improve” algorithms. From 1986 to 2000, the “improve” remained a relatively stable proportion while the percentages of other motivations fluctuated significantly. After 2000, the proportions of all motivations showed little change, indicating that while algorithms may have been updated, their mention motivations remained consistent.

Figure 1. The distribution of motivations yearly

The proportions of different mention motivations of algorithms with high mention frequency

We used the method of Wang & Zhang (2020) to measure the influence of algorithms and selected the top 100 entities as high-impact algorithms. For each algorithm, we calculated the percentage of sentences mentioning them under different motivations and presented the top five algorithms with the highest proportion of each motivation in Table 3. NB and C4.5 get the highest proportion of “mention” and “use”, respectively. The transformer has the highest “compare” and “improve” proportions.

Overall, algorithms with more proportion of “compare” and “improve” are mainly deep learning algorithms and do not include traditional machine learning algorithms. The longer the history of an algorithm, the higher proportion of “mention” it has; the lower the proportion of “compare” and “improve”

it has. It suggests that authors tend to use different motivations when describing different algorithms, and it is therefore valuable to differentiate algorithm influence based on motivations.

Table 3. The top five algorithms get the highest proportion of each motivation

No.	Mention	Use	Compare	Improve
1	NB	C4.5	transformer	transformer
2	CYK	roBerta	KNS	ILP
3	DCG	L-BFGS	Bertlarge	GAN
4	EM	Bi-RNN	DCG	GCN
5	DT	Bert base	Bi-GRU	Bi-GRU

Note: NB(naive bayes), CYK(cocke younger kasami), DCG(definite clause grammar), EM(expectation maximization), DT(decision tree), L-BFGS(limited-memory broyden fletcher goldfarb shanno), Bi-RNN (bi-directional recurrent neural network), KNS(kneser ney smoothing), Bi-GRU (bidirectional gated recurrent unit), ILP(integer linear programming), GAN (generative adversarial network), GCN(graph convolutional network).

Conclusion

Taking the NLP domain as an example, we extracted algorithms and explored the motivation for mentioning them in academic papers. We found that authors mainly use algorithms directly, followed by mentioning, comparing and improving them. The proportions of the four motivations changed slightly over time. For high-impact algorithms, grammatic algorithms and classical machine learning algorithms have a higher proportion of “mentions”, while algorithms getting more proportion of “use”, “compare”, and “improve” included more deep learning algorithms.

The limitation of this article is that each sentence was only assigned one motivation. In the future, we plan to improve the results of the mention motivation identification and use them to evaluate the academic influence of algorithms.

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